

SOLAR ENERGY IN THE PRIMARY PROCESSING OF MULBERRY SILKWORM COCOONS

R.M.Mirsaatov¹

Dsc, professor

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5745-4431>

e-mail: mirsaatov61@mail.ru

G. Sh. Sultankhodjaeva¹

independent applicant

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-7201-0803>

e-mail: gsultanxojaeva@gmail.com¹

Tashkent State Transport University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14900060>

Abstract. There are unlimited sources of energy. Examples include solar energy. One of the promising directions for reducing energy resource consumption in the processes of moring and complete drying of cocoons is the use of solar radiation energy through photovoltaic systems to convert solar energy into electrical energy. The processes of primary treatment using both direct and indirect solar energy impact on live cocoons have been studied.

Keywords: energy resources, cocoon moring, drying, solar radiation energy, sericulture, analysis, comparison, air layer, humidity.

Currently, the introduction of new technology that meets the demands of the time requires more and more electricity in all areas of production. The main sources of electrical energy are fuels such as oil, natural gas, and coal. The amount of these organic fuels in the Earth's crust is limited, their extraction is becoming increasingly difficult, and their cost continues to rise.

Scientists are tasked with directly generating electrical energy and finding alternative sources of energy. Indeed, there are virtually unlimited sources of energy. Examples include solar and wind energy, as well as the energy generated by ocean tides, and other forms of renewable energy. According to researchers, energy consumption is expected to increase by 90 percent by 2030. This could lead to a significant rise in carbon dioxide emissions into the atmosphere and further deterioration of the environmental situation. To address this issue, it is planned that by 2030, 40 percent of the required fuel will be provided through the use of renewable sources of thermal energy, such as solar, wind, hydropower, and biological methods of energy generation. In this regard, alternative energy sources are actively being integrated and widely applied in the energy system [1].

Uzbekistan is one of the first countries in Central Asia to enter a new stage of solar energy development, based on its own scientific research. Scientists are conducting effective studies on the rational use of the vast potential of solar energy. For more than ten years, systems for providing hot water and heating to residential and social facilities using solar energy have been developed and experimentally used based on the scientific developments of Uzbek scientists. Solar installations for heating water have also been installed in several regions. The latest developments by Uzbek scientists are also used in agriculture. In the Republic, for moring mulberry silkworm cocoons, all primary processing bases use physically outdated conveyor cocoon dryers that treat the cocoons with hot air. To mor one ton of live cocoons in these dryers, 85-90 kg of diesel fuel and 70-75 kW of electrical energy are consumed.[3].

To increase the volume of cocoon production, improve their quality, and reduce energy resource consumption for their primary processing, along with other measures, the development and implementation of modern energy-saving technologies is required. One of the promising directions for reducing energy resource consumption in the primary processing of cocoons in our Republic is the use of solar radiation energy. For this purpose, there are photovoltaic systems that convert solar energy into electrical energy. These systems include solar panels, an energy storage system, and a device that converts direct current into alternating current. A

photovoltaic system is long-lasting, does not require specialized maintenance, and pays back the costs within a few years. [6].

The primary processing of mulberry silkworm cocoons occurs during the sunniest months of the year — May and June, which provides an excellent opportunity to extensively use solar energy for this purpose. Researchers from the Scientific Research Institute have conducted studies to develop efficient devices for the primary processing of cocoons using solar energy. Both direct and indirect methods of utilizing solar energy for cocoon drying, as well as their combined application, were tested. Additionally, the technical capabilities of the device were examined. The device is equipped with an automatic control system that maintains the required temperature at a set level. On sunny days, the panels supply electricity to the device and store energy for autonomous operation. On cloudy days, when the panels cannot provide sufficient energy, a diesel generator automatically turns on and operates until the energy from the solar panels is restored. During this time, the batteries store energy from the network for subsequent autonomous operation. The technical potential of solar energy is three times greater than the amount of energy currently used from all available sources [2, 4].

A solar installation is used for the primary processing of mulberry silkworm cocoons. It consists of a thermally insulated chamber mounted on a trolley, with the upper part covered by two glass plates with an air layer between them. Inside the chamber, there is a mesh drum that rotates on pulleys. The drum consists of two nested cylinders, with the cocoons placed inside the inner cylinder. Heated air under pressure is supplied from both sides of the smaller cylinder through a fan, using pipes connected to the central channel of the drum. The hot, high-pressure air in the central channel passes between the cocoons, moving outward and evenly drying them. The drum with the cocoons rotates via a shaft driven by an electric motor. The trolley is equipped with four rotating wheels. On the upper platform of the trolley, there is a screw lift mechanism that moves the chamber along the vertical axis. The chamber is connected to an electronic control unit and a computer. Using this device, the cocoons placed in the mesh drum undergo complete drying through the simultaneous use of both direct (direct exposure to solar energy) and indirect (supplying electric heaters with electrical energy via a photovoltaic system) solar energy. For the complete drying of mulberry silkworm cocoons, parameters such as the temperature of the hot air, the rotation speed of the mesh drum, and the moisture content of the cocoons are controlled. These parameters are monitored through a computer connected to the electronic control unit.

As is well known, maintaining the quality of produced cocoons largely depends on the methods of their preparation and primary processing. Therefore, during the research, experiments were conducted to compare the quality indicators of cocoons processed using the new solar energy technology and those processed in the SK-150K conveyor unit for cocoon drying. The main quality indicators of cocoons, such as the yield of raw silk and silk products, were higher for cocoons processed using the new technology. According to the new technology, the yield of raw silk and silk products is 43.54% and 52.13%, respectively, compared to 41.01% and 49.82% for the SK-150K unit. Overall, even with similar indicators, it can be stated that the cocoon processing method based on the new technology is more efficient. Existing methods and equipment for the primary processing of mulberry silkworm cocoons were analyzed, and their advantages and disadvantages were assessed. As a result, it was shown that the most optimal solution to address issues in this area is the use of solar energy for the primary processing of cocoons. A modernized device for processing mulberry silkworm cocoons, utilizing solar energy, has been developed for optimal energy resource consumption. It addresses practical challenges by accelerating the complete drying process and ensuring the long-term preservation of the quality of processed cocoons.

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